

“God’s Will”: My Family Connection to Confederate General Robert E. Lee
by Brian Paul Kaess

In this paper, I will show what was once thought of as a mere 'related by marriage' connection to famous Confederate General Robert E. Lee, became, after investigating a family tale, something more substantial. Through careful research and using genealogy tools such as FSFT (FamilySearch Family Tree). I was able to demonstrate a kith-and-kin style relationship to Lee. I will also explore the intersection between Genealogy and Historiography and how they complement each other.

Growing up, I had heard of Robert E. Lee (1807-1870) as a great Confederate General who had fought nobly for the South, in what others would later term 'the Lost Cause.' He was renowned for his tactics at Battles such as Second Manassas and Chancellorsville. I even visited the Manassas Battlefield Park when I was a young soldier serving in the U.S. Army. Also, as you may recall, Lee lived in Alexandria, Virginia, for at least a part of his youth. I married my 1st wife Ellen Byrd Elliott at the Alexandria courthouse on October 10, 1986. So, these small events were like 'walking in the footsteps of history.'

But little did I know of any significant family connection to him. That was how it was until about 2014 when I started putting together a family book on my Swartz & Ochiltree Virginia ancestors and realized I was related to Lee through marriage because of our connection to the Bolling Family, which is rich in Virginia family connections to begin with. We were related by marriage to Gen. Robert E. Lee (by 23 steps). I thought that was nice, but didn't think we had any personal contact with Lee.

Boy was I wrong. In about 2017, Brenda Dulaney, a resident of Vancouver, WA, and a cousin of mine through the Major family, told me that the Majors (parents of my ancestor John Edward Major) were wealthy and owned a hotel in *antebellum* Virginia. Robert E. Lee was a guest there. Brenda Dulaney also says that the Majors were friends with Robert E. Lee. She also says the hotel was near Charlottesville, Virginia, although this could have been my misinterpretation.

Now let us look at Ella Major Zimmerman, sister to my 2nd gr. grandfather John Edward Major. The obituary of Ella, found in *The Times Dispatch* (of Richmond) dated August 18, 1941, confirms part of this story. But the *obit* says that the hotel was in Lexington, not Charlottesville. My bad! It says that Ella, my 2nd gr. grandaunt, was a friend to Lee. Ella was a longtime member of the *United Daughters of the Confederacy* (UDC) as well. It appears she knew him when he was president of Washington College. In addition, there is a Rockbridge County Deed that says that William W. Major (my 3rd gr. grandfather) and Charles T. O' Ferral jointly bought the *Lexington Hotel* from G.A. White in October 1867. Charles T. O' Farrel was later Governor of Virginia. There is an image below of a street in Lexington, Virginia, circa 1865-66, with the *Lexington Hotel* on the right-center of the street. It also has G.A. White printed on the hotel sign. There is also an image of Ella Major Zimmerman. This helps confirm the story a bit.

Lisa McCown of Washington & Lee University says that in volume 4 of Douglas Southall Freeman's, *R. E. Lee*¹, it states on page 230 that Lee resided at the *Lexington Hotel* until the arrival of his family. It reads, 'Rising early at the *Lexington Hotel*, where he resided until the arrival of his family, he proceeded afoot to the college.' Also on page 230, 'Unless there were religious or academic exercises that he felt called upon to attend, he remained in his room at the hotel after supper.' On page 229², it reads 'Returning to Lexington on September 30, and taking lodgings at the hotel, General Lee was ready for his inauguration.' On page 241³, 'Custis was with the General at the hotel now, having been elected professor.'

In a circa 1865-66 image, the sign in front of the *Lexington Hotel* has the name G. A. White on it. G. is for Gustavus. He is the person who sold the hotel to my ancestor in 1867. in *Recollections and Letters of Robert E Lee* (1904)⁴ his son Robert E. Lee mentions a letter his father wrote on September 15, 1865, 'He will find me at the *Lexington Hotel* ... I wish you were all with me. I feel very solitary and miss you all dreadfully' and on October 3, 1865, he wrote, 'I am living at the *Lexington Hotel*, and he must come there if he comes up.' ...

Furthermore, my 3rd gr. grandfather Robert E. Gibboney (1810-1867) was a Delegate to the Virginia General Assembly from 1865-67. He was also a CSA Prices Commissioner during the war (an appointed office) and he and his brother Maj. William Gibboney (1815-1901), a Confederate BQM, were responsible for making Wytheville, Virginia, a major Confederate supply depot during the war- per my cousin Dr. Mark Baldwin, D.O.; Lee must have depended on such supply depots to feed his army. William was always penning letters to the Confederate QM Corps. Robert was also involved in impressment activities, per Clayta Bryant of the *Wythe County Genealogical and Historical Association* in Wytheville, Virginia. My 1st cousin once removed Sister Elizabeth Anne Swartz, SSND, (Swartz family historian), mentions in her *Continuation* document, that Gibboney wore the uniform of a Confederate Colonel. So he appeared to be firmly in the Confederate fold, at the highest echelons. So there would appear to be, at least for him, ripe opportunity to meet Lee.

Additionally, Robert E. Gibboney died at the *Exchange Hotel* in Richmond on April 7, 1867. Lee was known to attend parties in the parlor of the *Exchange Hotel* with former officers of his entourage. Was Robert E. Gibboney there? I don't know, but we do know that young ladies were present. I believe he likely was there, and as a former Confederate appointed official, knew how to sow his social graces with Lee. His image is shown as well², with slight color added.

Moreover, Major William Gibboney's son, and my 1st cousin three times removed, Pvt. Albert Haller Gibboney (1843-1917) had fought at the Battle of Gettysburg (1863) and helped carry a wounded Gen. Henry Heth off the battlefield on the 1st day, making himself a war hero. Heth had been struck by a bullet during the fighting near McPherson's Ridge,

¹ See *R.E. Lee* (1935) by Douglas Southall Freeman, p.230.

² *Ibid.* p. 229.

³ *Ibid.* p. 241.

⁴ See *Recollections and Letters of Robert E Lee* (1904) by Robert Edward Lee, Jr.

knocked unconscious, and carried off the field by Gibboney and others. Lee may have been aware of this. Heth, who survived the war, once wrote a sparkling recommendation on behalf of Gibboney, his former young aide.

During the *Wytheville Raid* (1863), William Gibboney's house along Tazewell street was used to help mount a defense for the rebels, and it is from this building that a bullet was believed to have been fired that killed Union Colonel John Toland⁵. This building was later known as 'the burnt lot.' Furthermore, he owned a house along Main street, which was also burned, later known as the *Haller-Gibboney Rock House Museum*. At the outset of the battle, the Union cavalry, upon entering town, were ambushed by Confederate soldiers, Home Guard, and local citizens, yet ended in the Union taking the town⁶.

Another relative was Confederate Surgeon Dr. Jacob Draper Haller (1796-1877), from Wytheville, Virginia, and my 1st cousin four times removed. He was married to Priscilla 'Cindy 'Malinda' Nye, a daughter of Capt. John Peter Nye. She was known for 'shouting' at her slaves. His medical skills would have been in constant use during the turbulent period of the American Civil War (ACW). An experienced physician, it is possible he may have come to the attention of Lee.

There was also Brigadier General William Robinson Terry (1824-1888), last commander of the famed 'Stonewall Brigade' and future U.S. Congressman from Wytheville, Virginia⁷. He oversaw remnants of the brigade at battles such as Cold Harbor and the defense of Petersburg. Lee might have had a clue who he was. His son Benjamin Wigginton Terry (1853-1940) was married to Carolyn Lafayette Gibboney (1863-1917), daughter of Major William Gibboney, my ancestor. This was an example of intermarriage among children of members of the former Confederate Officer Corps where one, Carolyn, is my *blood* relative. Indeed, it is through General Terry's wife, Emily 'Emma' Williams Wigginton (1829-1909) that I am related by marriage to Pocahontas by 18 steps. Emma is my 5th cousin four times removed.

A near-miss relative, so to speak, that nearly crossed paths with Lee, was my 2nd gr. grandfather Prof. Joseph Godfrey Swartz (1847-1887) of Rockbridge County, Virginia⁸. He served in the 'Boys Company' or Junior Reserves of the Rockbridge County Virginia Reserves of the CSA Army, seeing action in the Valley Campaign of 1864 as a mere private. After the war, he had studied and later taught in the school of his future brother-in-law Rev. William Henry Ochiltree (1842-1890), aka 'The Blind Preacher.' He then studied at Washington & Lee University (class of 1873) and became a Latin instructor at VMI, but this was well after Lee's tenure at these prestigious institutions. The Grey Ghost indeed!

So, with all these real-world connections or possible 'ships passing in the night' scenarios between my family and Lee, I began to view the personage of Lee and the Confederacy not merely as a titanic-style struggle between the Old South and the North on issues such as slavery, right of secession, states rights, etc., but as a more homespun-

⁵ See *Wythe County Virginia Bicentennial History* (1989) by Mary B. Kegley.

⁶ See *Early Adventurers on the Western Waters* (1980) by Mary B. Kegley, pp. 145-6.

⁷ See *Generals in Gray: Lives of the Confederate Commanders* (1959) by Ezra J. Warner.

⁸ See *History of the house of Ochiltree of Ayrshire, Scotland : with the genealogy of the families of those who came to America and of some of the allied families, 1124-1916*, (1916) by Clementine Brown Railey, p. 126.

affair, where Lee figures as a more human figure, almost invoking *pathos* when he finds himself a bit lonely and isolated, even at the *Lexington Hotel*. Lee appears more to me now as a real person, and less of an abstraction found amidst the clash of North & South. On the flip side, with Lee virtually enmeshed with my Major/Gibboney family entourage, I felt like they were standings on the shoulders of giants- i.e. Lee.

Also, by using BYU Relative Finder, I also located 'ol Robert as my 6th cousin five times removed, through the common ancestor William Randolph (1572-1660) of England. This pretty much confirms that Lee was a *blood* relative. This was on the Major/Tinsley side of my mom's family. How about a round of applause for that one!

Therefore, we see here how Genealogy can serve as a gateway to historical context. Genealogical research focuses on tracing lineage, kinship, and familial ties. But when those ties intersect with prominent historical figures like Lee, the implications go far beyond ancestry charts.

For instance, It transforms abstract historical narratives into intimate family stories, making national events feel personal. It reveals social networks. Kinship ties can uncover networks of influence, loyalty, and power-especially in elite families of the antebellum South. The Majors were always loyal to Lee, and doted on him accordingly. The Gibboney's, Anglican descendants of the Kyle clan in Scotland, who had been rewarded by the Crown in the British Isles, seemed to have kept their influence in the South during the time of the American Civil War (ACW)- perhaps because people in positions of power and influence, like Lee, rewarded those with English royal connections. Like my Philosophy Professor James Dye once told us, once heaping scorn on antiquity: 'nothing changes.'

Moreover, Genealogy contributes to historiography in several nuanced ways. One example is Source Material: Genealogical records (wills, letters, census data- in my case deeds) serve as primary sources for historians reconstructing social, political, or cultural contexts. There is also Authority and Legitimacy: As seen in ancient historiography (e.g., Herodotus), where genealogy was often used rhetorically to establish authority or justify political claims. I can't say my genealogy research gained me any political points, but it did enable me to join a lineage society, the *Military Order of Stars and Bars*, based on proven ancestry to Robert E. Gibboney. How about some kudos for that!

Furthermore, Genealogy research challenges or confirms narratives: A genealogical link might support or complicate prevailing historical interpretations of class, race, or regional identity or the story itself. Lisa McCown's help at Washington & Lee University, when she confirmed that Lee had stayed at the *Lexington Hotel*, got the ball rolling. Specifically, when I found the deed to the *Lexington Hotel* in Lexington, Virginia, with my ancestor William Watson Major's name on it, all the pieces of the puzzle started coming together.

Brenda Dulaney's tale that the Major's were friends to Lee now appeared to be much more than just a yarn. The newspaper article with Ella Major Zimmerman, where she is mentioned as Lee's friend, merely cemented this. To sum up, my Virginia family is not just related by marriage to the Grey Ghost, but also are *blood* relatives as well; Indeed, they were even F.A.N. Club members to him, which is wonderful to note in genealogy. Therefore, they were definitely friends and associates of Robert E Lee. Two or three of my Virginia ancestors definitely knew General Lee at a personal level, and four more may have crossed paths with Lee or achieved 'honorable mention' from him. So we see, now and then, how Confederate Ghosts from the past continue to pop up in our family story.

Upper Left: Lexington Hotel with white sign in front on right side of street. (Credit: 'Lexington Hotel during the Civil War,' *Encyclopedia Virginia* at encyclopediavirginia.org). William Watson Major, Brian's 3rd great grandfather, was co-owner of this hotel and he and his family waited upon Lee when he stayed in Lexington. Charles T. O'Farrel, later governor of Virginia, was also co-owner. The Rockbridge County Deed of the hotel, with both their names on it, demonstrated the powerful political connections that the Major's, affluent themselves, had at this time.

Upper Right: Robert E. Gibboney, Brian's 3rd great-grandfather. (Credit: *Vol. 4 Early Adventurers on the Western Waters*, p. 145 by Mary B. Kegley. He was CSA Prices Commissioner during the American Civil War (ACW), as well as a Delegate to the Virginia Assembly from 1865-67. This meant that he sat in the chamber that Thomas Jefferson designed. He and his brother William Gibboney both received Confederate Pardons from Pres. Andrew Johnson and were both involved in Freedman's Bureau activities in reconstruction-era Wytheville, Virginia. The Gibboney's had owned slaves during the *antebellum* period and were known as sort of 'landgrabbers.'

Upper Left: Ella Major Zimmerman. (Credit: *The Times Dispatch* (Richmond, Virginia), August 18 1941, Monday p. 7). She was Brian's 2nd gr. grand aunt and friend to Robert E. Lee in his later years. She was the sister of John Edward Major (1848-19139, Brian's direct ancestor and also a member of the *United Daughter of the Confederacy* (UDC)).

Upper Right: Confederate General Robert E. Lee, in one of his more iconic images. (Credit: Public Domain). He was kith & kin to the Major's of Lexington, Virginia, and may have crossed paths with Robert E. Gibboney in Richmond. Lee undoubtedly knew Brig. General William Terry, because the latter was the last commander of the famed 'Stonewall Brigade.' Ella Major Zimmerman knew him in his older years when she was a young lady. Pvt. Albert Haller Gibboney, Brian's cousin, served on the same battlefield as Lee at Gettysburg and helped save one his Generals, Henry Heth, by carrying him from the field with others.

Upper Left: Major William Gibboney, Brian's 3rd gr. granduncle, in his later years. (Credit: *Vol. 4 Early Adventurers on the Western Waters*, p. 146 by Mary B. Kegley). He and his brother Robert E. Gibboney were responsible for making Wytheville, Virginia, a major Confederate Supply Depot. He may have also served on the Confederate General Staff.

Upper Right: Brigadier General William R. Terry. (Credit: Wikipedia Commons). An allied family member, he was last commander of remnants of the famed Stonewall Brigade and undoubtedly knew Lee. He had fought in various battles- from 1st Bull Run to Cold Harbor. He surrendered with Lee's Army at Appomattox Court House on April 8, 1865. He was a future U.S. Congressman from Virginia and a staple in Wytheville politics. His house in Wytheville, Virginia still stands.

Top Left & Right: Dr. Jacob Draper Haller & his wife Priscilla 'Cindy' Malinda Nye. (Credit: Find a Grave at findagrave.com, photos added by Jeff Gray). A resident of Wytheville, Virginia and a Confederate Surgeon, his expertise likely saved lives during the American Civil War (ACW). He and his young, tempestuous wife Priscilla Malinda 'Cindy' Nye may have been quite an *antebellum* pair.

19882 Wytheville, VA- The South Western Bank of Virginia \$5 Proof
Jones BW60-25

Originally known as the Bank of Wytheville when it was authorized in 1852, this firm became the South Western Bank of Virginia the following year. Florence Nightingale's portrait is seen to the right of center. Thomas J. Morrison (1805-65) is seen at bottom left and Robert Gibboney (1812-67) at bottom right. PCGS grades this note **Apparent Very Choice New 64** due to a tape repair at the bottom margin and internal tears as well as 6 POC. (275-375)

Top: *South Western Bank of Virginia \$5 Bill.* (Credit: *Wytheville Historical & Genealogical Society*). Brian's direct ancestor Robert E. Gibboney was a banker at this institution. He is shown in bottom right of note. Florence Nightingale's image is shown, her being a famous nurse during the Crimean War (1853-1856). The American Civil War (ACW) was soon to follow. Both were considered modern wars, and the former was considered the last stand for Chivalry, with the 'infamous' 'Charge of the Light Brigade.' Perhaps, it is not such a reach to consider all wars in such a light- i.e. fruitless.